

EXAMINING PACKAGE TOURISTS' EXPERIENCE ON OVERALL PACKAGE TOUR SATISFACTION AND BEHAVIORAL INTENTIONS: FIRST-TIME *VERSUS* REPEAT PACKAGE TOURISTS

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Abstract

This paper examines the influence of package tour experience dimensions (i.e., educational, entertainment, escapism, and esthetic experience) on tour satisfaction and behavioral intentions by comparing first-time and repeat package tourists. For this purpose, a self-administered questionnaire was distributed to tourists visiting Istanbul with a package tour. A convenience sampling was adopted and a total of 375 usable questionnaires was included in the analysis. Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling approach was used to examine the data. The study findings indicated that education and esthetic experience affects overall package tour satisfaction for first-time tourists; entertainment and esthetic experience affects overall package tour satisfaction for repeat tourists. Furthermore, the overall package tour satisfaction mediates between these variables and behavioral intentions for both groups. The findings have suggested theoretical and managerial implications, limitations, and suggestions for further studies.

Keywords: Package tour; Package tour satisfaction; Behavioral intentions.

EXAMINANDO A EXPERIÊNCIA DOS TURISTAS QUANTO AO PACOTE TURÍSTICO EM RELAÇÃO À SATISFAÇÃO GERAL E EXPECTATIVAS DE COMPORTAMENTO DO PACOTE: TURISTAS DE PACOTE TURÍSTICO INICIANTES *VERSUS* USUÁRIOS FREQUENTES

Resumo

Este artigo examina a influência das dimensões da experiência do pacote turístico (ou seja, experiência educacional, de entretenimento, escapismo e estética) na satisfação do passeio e nas intenções comportamentais, comparando os turistas que viajam pela primeira vez e os que repetem. Para tanto, um questionário autoaplicável foi distribuído aos turistas que visitam Istambul por meio de pacote turístico. Uma amostra de conveniência foi adotada e um total de 375 questionários utilizáveis foi incluído na análise. A abordagem de Modelagem de Equações Estruturais de Mínimos Quadrados Parciais foi usada para examinar os dados. Os resultados do estudo indicaram que a educação e a experiência estética afetam a satisfação geral do pacote turístico para os turistas de primeira viagem; o entretenimento e a experiência estética afetam a satisfação geral do pacote turístico para os turistas que voltam. Além disso, a satisfação geral com o pacote turístico faz a mediação entre essas variáveis e as intenções comportamentais de ambos os grupos. Os resultados sugeriram implicações teóricas e gerenciais, limitações e sugestões para estudos futuros.

Palavras-chave: Pacote de Viagem em Grupo; Satisfação do Consumidor de Turismo; Lealdade do Consumidor Turista.

EXAMINANDO LA EXPERIENCIA DE LOS TURISTAS DE PAQUETES SOBRE LA SATISFACCIÓN GENERAL Y LAS INTENCIONES DE COMPORTAMIENTO DEL TOUR DE PAQUETES: TURISTAS DE PAQUETES POR PRIMERA VEZ *VERSUS* USUÁRIOS FRECUENTES

Resumen

Este documento examina la influencia de las dimensiones de la experiencia del paquete turístico (es decir, educación, entretenimiento, escapismo y experiencia estética) en la satisfacción del recorrido y las intenciones de comportamiento al comparar los turistas que realizan paquetes por primera vez y los que repiten. Con este fin, se distribuyó un cuestionario autoadministrado a los turistas que visitaban Estambul a través de un paquete turístico. Se adoptó una muestra de conveniencia y se incluyó en el análisis un total de 375 cuestionarios utilizables. Para examinar los datos se utilizó el enfoque de Modelado de ecuaciones estructurales de mínimos cuadrados parciales. Los resultados del estudio indicaron que la educación y la experiencia estética afectan la satisfacción general del paquete turístico para los turistas primerizos; El entretenimiento y la experiencia estética afectan la satisfacción general del paquete turístico para los turistas que repiten. Además, la satisfacción general del paquete turístico media entre estas variables y las intenciones de comportamiento de ambos grupos. Los hallazgos han sugerido implicaciones teóricas y administrativas, limitaciones y sugerencias para estudios adicionales.

Palabras clave: Paquete de viaje grupal; Satisfacción del consumidor turístico; Fidelización del consumidor turista.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Package tours refer to an assembly of tourism products and services (Räikkönen, 2014) offered by tour operators and travel agencies in a destination (Caber & Albayrak, 2018). It encompasses services including pre-tour briefing, airport/plane, hotel, restaurants, coach, sightseeing, shopping opportunities, optional tours, and other services offered in the destination (Wang, Hsieh, & Huan, 2000).

Bowie and Chang (2005) further included in package tours the services of the tour leader and natural or cultural attractions. Overall, these components of package tours create experience in the destination for tourists (Stamboulis & Skayannis, 2003) which is known as "subjective experiences" (Komppula, 2006). During the package tour, tourists visit some places in a limited time, and they experience different products and services in the destination (Enoch, 1996).

Package tours may develop tourism destinations by improving its attractiveness to international visitors (Liao & Chuang, 2020). Furthermore, package tours are essential for the long-term success of the destination and the increasing profit of the tour operators (Leguma, 2013). To make it continuousness, they should ensure package tourists to be satisfied from the destination and their experience because satisfied tourists package tour can play a pivotal role in revisiting the destination and repurchasing the same package tour product as well as recommending it around of them (Bowie & Chang, 2005).

Xu and Chan (2010) revealed that services experience influences package tour satisfaction and indicated that tourists tend to repurchase the same package tour and likely recommend the package tour to others owing to overall package tour satisfaction. In this context, it can be remarked that tourist satisfaction and loyalty are the two main objectives which destination managers and service providers are focusing on and trying to succeed in.

Also, tourist satisfaction plays a major role in decreasing price elasticity (Fornell, Mithas, Morgeson, & Krishnan, 2006), reducing transaction costs of products and services (Yang & Peterson, 2004), improving the existing capacity of customers (Uncles, East, & Lomax, 2013) and a strong reputation in the market (Walsh, Mitchell, Jackson, & Beatty, 2009).

There is a growing body of literature that recognizes the importance of package tours. Previous studies have been conducted on the contents of a package tour (Enoch, 1996), tour guides' performance on tourist satisfaction (Bowie & Chang, 2005; Chang, 2006; Huang, Hsu & Chan, 2010), satisfaction measurement of package tours (Geva & Goldman, 1991), the motivation and satisfaction of package

tourists (Ross & Iso-Ahola, 1991), tourists' perceptions of package tour service quality (Chang, 2009), participant behavior of package tourists (Fomiatti, 2008) and the effects of tour quality and tourist satisfaction on tourist loyalty (Lee, Jeon, & Kim, 2011).

However, a small number of researchers have focused on the package tour experience, and less attention yet has been paid to the impact of package tour experience on package tour satisfaction and behavioral intentions of tourists.

Recently, many destinations use different marketing strategies to attract more potential visitors and to generate repeat visitors (Lin & Morais, 2010). These destinations mostly face some difficulties in attracting these visitors due to alternative competitive destinations (Castro, Armario, & Ruiz, 2007).

Thus, tourism practitioners pay attention to identify which factors determine intention to revisit of tourists to evaluate destination economic sustainability (Petrick, Morais, & Norman, 2001) because repeat tourists are a stable source of incomes for a destination and provide fewer costs for tourist retention (Cossio-Silva, Revilla-Camacho, & Vega-Vázquez, 2019). They stay more in a single destination and than first-timers (Yang, Wong, & Zhang, 2011).

Additionally, tourist experience may vary from tourists to tourists in the destination and they can differ in terms of repeat or non-repeat tourists (Kozak, Huan, & Beaman, 2002) as well as the level of satisfaction and behavioral intentions (Shavanddasht & Allan, 2018).

Understanding these differences have frequently been used as one of the key attributes in developing marketing and management strategies. These also improve some tourist motivation and decision-making theories (Li, Cheng, Kim, & Petrick, 2008).

While prior researchers have found significant differences between first-time and repeat visitors, they ignored to determine the main reasons for these differences. Most of the studies have revealed that repeat visitors tend to purchase a product or service in the future than first-time visitors (Petrick, Morais, & Norman 2001).

Therefore, the fact that examining differences between the first time and repeat visitors is crucial for destination managers and service providers (Shavanddasht & Allan, 2018) to understand better the satisfaction with package tour experience and behavioral intention.

Prior research conducted in various tourism settings generally confirms that there is a relationship between tourism experience and satisfaction on intent to revisit and recommend to others (Rowley, 1999; Kim & Brown, 2012; Nobar & Rostamzadeh, 2018; Serra-Cantalops, Ramon-Cardona, & Salvi, 2018).

However, a comprehensive study is not

conducted on the mediating effect of overall package tour satisfaction on the relationship between package tour experience and behavioral intentions of first time and repeat package tourists.

Moreover, although there are several tourism studies about repeat and non-repeat tourists' level of satisfaction and revisit intentions, there is no single study that has compared package tour experience, overall package tour satisfaction, and behavioral intentions of first-time and repeat package tourists.

The present study fills a gap in the literature by providing additional evidence about the relationship between these variables in terms of visit frequency. Finally, despite the abundance of tourists visiting Istanbul mostly with package tours, no studies have been conducted on package tourist experience in Istanbul.

Therefore, this study aims to (1) investigate the impact of the overall package tour satisfaction on the relationship between package tour experience and behavioral intentions for the first time and repeat tourists visiting Istanbul with package tours and (2) to analyze the differences and similarities of first-time and repeat tourists' package tour experience, overall package tour satisfaction, and behavioral intentions.

This research has important implications for the relevant experience economy model and practitioners. First, we used this model in a package tour context and the findings will justify this model as result of inspection. By doing so, this research extends the current model by applying to different tourism experience area such as package tour. Second, practical implications will be extremely useful for travel companies which offer package tour in terms of understanding which dimensions of package tour experience determine satisfaction and loyalty.

2 CONCEPTUAL BACKGROUND AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

2.1 Package Tour Experience

The first package tour was organized in 1841 by Thomas Cook and prepared some inclusive tours to some regions of Europe (Polat & Arslan, 2019). Thus, Thomas Cook is regarded as the first inventor of the package tour. As a result of package trips, it has emerged that such tours can be made for commercial purposes due to arousing the satisfaction of the tour attendees.

The rapid development of the package tours and spreading to broad public masses have started in Western European countries after the Second World War II. After 1945, a large number of military aircraft were allowed to be used on the condition of organizing

package tours.

Organized tours with charter flights from Northern European countries to Southern European countries have been organized in 1948 (Ataberk, 2007). So, package tours have been the most popular travel experience and core service offered by travel companies since the 1950s (Albayrak et al., 2016).

It is also the most remarkable part of the commercial tourism industry (Cetin & Yarcin, 2017). From past to present, package tours have been commonly used by tourists for some reasons such as developing bonds of friendship, lower price than an individual trip, many services in a single product, and is accompanied by a guide or escort.

The common reason for choosing a package tour is an economic benefit (Chang, 2007). Furthermore, tourists expect from their package tour to be a memorable, comfortable, and stress-free atmosphere guided generally by a professional escort (Duke & Persia, 1993).

The package tour is a basic service product offered by tour companies (Caber & Albayrak, 2018). The package tour is defined by WTO (World Tourism Organization) as "a single product provided by a tour operator which elaborates it and sells it directly or through travel agencies, in which travelers receive a combination of products associated to a trip such as transport, accommodation sightseeing, entertainment, etc. and other goods and services at will" (World Tourism Organization, 2015). Sheldon (1986) further defined a package tour as a single product at a single price including the components of travel services such as accommodation, transportation, entertainment, and food and beverages.

Substantially, there are two types of predominant package tours including "basic package tours" and "all-inclusive package tours" (Mok & Armstrong, 1995; Wong & Kwong, 2004). Today, "daily tours" are also regarded as one of the most important package tours for tour companies due to their extra revenues (Caber & Albayrak, 2018).

A basic package tour generally includes only transportation and accommodation. Tourists can proceed at their leisure in the destination. The second type of package tour is the so-called all-inclusive package which includes a single price of tour involving transportation and accommodation, meals, and sightseeing, sometimes with a tour guide or tour escort service.

On these tours, services of transportation, accommodation, a professional tour guide, visits of cultural and historical sites, and food and beverage services are offered by a tour operator or travel agency (Stetic & Stanic, 2011). Therefore, the service experiences of these travel products are considered as

the most essential matters for tourists. Also, touristic products and quality of service are an element that adds value to the total package tour experience (Komppula, 2006).

Furhermore, a study by Martínez and Guillén (2007) investigated Spanish tourists visiting South America, Central America or Caribbean through package tour. They indicated that perceived quality of package tours are the major determinant of package tour satisfaction.

In tourism destinations, everything encountered by tourists leads to an experience (Karakuş, 2019; Stamboulis & Skayannis, 2003). Similarly, services offered in package tours are also considered as a tourist experience (Avci, 2019).

The package tour experience has been preferred among different market segments such as culture and heritage tourists (Hargrove, 2002). The package tour experience is a sensible and comprehensible way for tourists who visit various places at the destination in an assigned time. Also, the package tour is considered as a safe way to visit the destination (Enoch, 1996).

Another reason for choosing the package tour experience is personal safety (Wong & Kwong, 2004) as well as getting to know other members of package tours (Quiroga, 1991). Finally, package tourists desire to experience the natural environment and cultural values for a deep experience (Wong & Kwong, 2004).

Package tour has been investigated across various topics such as motivations of the tourists participating in package tours (Chang, 2007), service quality of package tours (Caber & Albayrak, 2018), market segmentation of package tours (Thomson & Pearce, 1980), the relationship between tourist guide and tourist satisfaction in package tours (Huang, Hsu & Chan, 2010) and loyalty of package tourists (Hanefors & Mossberg, 1999).

However, no studies have attempted to investigate experiential characteristics of package tours from the perspective of the experience economy in the literature despite that the experience economy has been investigated in a substantial number of studies regarding tourism experience (Andersson, 2007; Oh, Fiore, & Jeoung, 2007).

Following the pioneering work of Pine and Gilmore (1999), the experience economy is a proposed four-dimensional model (i.e. escapist, educational, esthetic, and entertainment experience) in which any of these dimensions can play a part in the active or passive sides of participation spectrums.

Escapist experiences are discussed as tourists being 'immersed' in the environment looking for something new and different and a feeling of escaping from their daily routine life. Entertainment experience refers to tourist's passive observes towards activities

and performances of others such as listening to music from buskers or watching a movie about the destination. *Educational experiences* arise when tourists desire to increase their knowledge or skill regarding the cultural and natural values of the destination. *Esthetic experience* is related to pleasure and enjoyment of tourists in the destination environment and it is on the passive side in the participation spectrums.

To the authors' knowledge, no one has yet attempted to assess the experience economy and its four-dimensional model from the perspective of the package tour. Considering the package tour offers a combination of different tourism products and services for tourists, package tour can be regarded as a significant part of the tourism experience and it is necessary to investigate it from the perspective of the experience economy (Aslan, Yaşar, Çetin, Akova, & Balık, 2015).

2.2 Package Tour Experience and Overall Package Tour Satisfaction

Several studies have attempted to explore the relationship between tourist experience and satisfaction (Çoban & Yetiş, 2019; Tan, 2017; Han, 2006). Pine and Gilmore (1999) stated that when customer experience increases, so do satisfaction. Satisfaction has been evaluated as a positive of a set of experiences as a result of appraisal (Hosany & Prayag 2013; Lima-Filho, Marchiotti, & Quevedo-Silva, 2012).

Baker and Crompton (2000) define tourist satisfaction as an emotional state of visitors after experiencing the trip to the destination. In tourism literature, it is based on pre-visit expectations and post-visit encounters (Asmelash & Kumar, 2019). It is also regarded as the cognitive and affective state of visitors (De Rojas & Camarero, 2008).

Satisfaction in tourism destinations is influenced by several factors such as expectations of visitors, destination image, service quality of destination, destination value, and destination experience (Shonk & Chelladurai, 2008; Wang, Zhang, Gu, & Zhen, 2009; Liu & Yen, 2010).

Studies in marketing (Caruana, 2002; Walter, Cleff, & Chu, 2013) and tourism literature (Cole & Scott, 2004; Han, 2006; Kao, Huang, & Wu, 2008; Tan, 2017; Albayrak, Caber, Hutcheson, & Moutinho, 2016), have pointed out that there is a relationship between experience and satisfaction. Satisfaction or dissatisfaction with the package tour experience occurs at the end of the trip (Xu & Chan, 2010).

Bowie and Chang (2005) indicated that package tour' service experiences of hedonism and enjoyment

affected the overall satisfaction of the destination. Also, satisfaction with tour experience leads to a successful vacation experience (Neal & Gursoy, 2008; Rääkkönen & Honkanen, 2013).

Previous studies investigated that the 4Es (educational, entertainment, escapism, and esthetic experience) have various influences on tourist satisfaction in different destinations (Oh, Fiore, & Jeoung, 2007; Hosany & Witham, 2009; Ho & Tsai, 2011; Quadri-Felitti & Fiore, 2013; Mahdzar et al., 2017). Therefore, the following hypotheses are formulated:

H1: Education experience influences overall package tour satisfaction.

H2: Entertainment experience influences overall package tour satisfaction.

H3: Escapism experience influences overall package tour satisfaction.

H4: Esthetic experience influences overall package tour satisfaction.

2.3 Overall Package Tour Satisfaction and Behavioral intentions

Empirical studies have well defined the relationship between satisfaction and behavioral intentions in both tourism (Baker & Crompton, 2000; Kozak & Rimmington, 2000; Prayag, Hosany, & Odeh, 2013) and marketing (Liljander & Strandvik, 1995; Anderson, 1995) literature. For example, Oliver (1997) defines behavioral intentions as "a stated likelihood to engage in a behavior" (p. 28). It represents an individual's efforts including recommending and revisit the destination to others (Ghorbanzade, Mehrani, & Rahehagh, 2019). According to Kozak and Rimmington (2000), when the level of overall satisfaction of tourists with destination experience increases, the intention to revisit the destinations also increases. So, loyalty is highly affected by the overall satisfaction of tourists (Bitner, 1990).

Various studies have also examined the link between tourist satisfaction and intention to recommend the destination to others (Chen & Chen, 2010). Chen and Chen (2010) concluded that there is a strong correlation between satisfaction and behavioral intentions. Pillai (2017) concluded that customer satisfaction in tourism and hospitality services leads to customer loyalty.

Furthermore, satisfaction is considered as a closer antecedent of behavioral intentions rather than tourist experience (Lin & Kuo, 2016). Customer satisfaction and loyalty is considered as the most important part of service quality in tourism and hospitality services (Loureiro, & González, 2012).

Several studies (Duman & Mattila, 2005; Yoon &

Uysal, 2005; Chi & Qu, 2008; Sun, Chi, & Xu, 2013) also attempted to show that tourist satisfaction impacts behavioral intentions (i.e. recommend and revisit). Tourists who are satisfied with their tourism experience are more likely to revisit and recommend the destination to others (Bigne, Sanchez, & Sanchez, 2001; Chen & Tsai, 2007) while dissatisfied ones are unlikely to choose the destination and also share their negative experience with others (Soscia, 2007). Therefore, given the conclusive relationship between tourist satisfaction and behavioral intentions, the current study proposes the following hypothesis.

H5: Overall package tour satisfaction positively influences behavioral intentions.

2.4 The Mediating Effect of Overall Package Tour Satisfaction on the Relationship Between Behavioral Intentions and Package Tour Experience

Previous studies have used satisfaction as a key construct modeling the relationship between tourist experience and behavioral intentions (Lin & Kuo, 2016; Gohary, Pourazizi, Madani, & Chan, 2020). In their study, Çetin and Akova (2016), revealed that tourist experience in package tours leads to the recommendation and is affected by positive, memorable, and enjoyable experiences.

Lin and Kuo (2016) argue that behavioral intentions are best clarified as concepts using both satisfaction and tourist experience. It is also stated that the relationships between tourist experience and behavioral intentions are entirely mediated by satisfaction.

Sangpikul (2018) explored the effects of travel experience on destination satisfaction and loyalty in an island destination. It was revealed that the relationship between travel experience and destination loyalty was mediated by tourist satisfaction. According to this study, when tourists experienced positive emotions they were satisfied with the destination and therefore this creates a destination loyalty through satisfied emotions.

Also, experience quality in the destination influenced behavioral intentions through destination satisfaction (Chen & Chen, 2010; Kim & Brown, 2012). Toyama and Yamada (2012) showed that satisfaction is considered as one of the most important mediators in examining experience and behavioral intentions. Hence, this current study formulates the following hypotheses for this construct:

H6: Overall package tour satisfaction mediates the effect on the relationship between education experience and behavioral intentions.

H7: Overall package tour satisfaction mediates the effect on the relationship between entertainment experience and behavioral intentions.

H8: Overall package tour satisfaction mediates the effect on the relationship between escapism experience and behavioral intentions.

H9: Overall package tour satisfaction mediates the effect on the relationship between esthetic experience and behavioral intentions.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Setting

With great potential in terms of heritage tourism and the largest city of Turkey (TUIK, 2018), Istanbul has been chosen as a research area since it has been registered on the World Heritage Sites List by UNESCO since 1985 (UNESCO, 2018). These World Heritage Sites are; "Sultanahmet Urban Archaeological Component Area", "Suleymaniye Mosque and its Associated Component Area", Zeyrek Mosque (Pantocrator Church) and its Associated Component Area" and "Istanbul Land Walls Component Area" (UNESCO, 2018).

Istanbul with its rich tangible and intangible heritage has hosted many different cultures and civilizations. Also, it houses different cultures, various ethnic groups, religions, and languages (Istanbul Provincial Directorate of Culture and Tourism, 2018).

In 2019, the total arrivals of foreigners in Istanbul were 13.778,748 and mostly are German (7.5%), Iranian (4.8%), and Russians (4.6%). Compared to 2018, there is an increase in foreigners (+11.52 percent) (Istanbul Provincial Directorate of Culture and Tourism, 2020).

3.2 Research Instrument

The purpose of this research is to reveal the effect of package tour experience on overall package tour satisfaction and the mediating effect of the overall package tour satisfaction on the relationship between package tour experience and behavioral intentions in terms of tourists' frequency of visits to the destination (first-time and repeat visitors).

A self-administered questionnaire survey was conducted to collect data from package tourists in Istanbul. Based on a review of the literature, a survey instrument was developed for this research and consisted of four sections.

In section 1, the package tour experience scale with 18 items modified from the findings obtained by Oh et al. (2007) was used. The package tour experiences scale consists of educational, entertainment, escapism, and esthetic experience dimensions. In section 2, the satisfaction scale adapted from Oliver (1980) with 4 items was used. In section 3, the behavioral intentions scale adapted from Zeithaml, Berry, and Parasuraman

(1996) with 5 items was used. In Section 4, to create profiles of the participants, a range of demographic data with 12 items such as age, gender, level of education, annual income, nationality, marital status, employment, mode of travel, number of times of participation in package tours, length of stay in a package tour, number of participants and number of visits was used.

Except for participant information measured by a categorical variable, all items of the first four parts are gauged by a 5-point Likert-type scale from "strongly disagree (=1)" to "strongly agree (=5)". To increase the reliability, exploratory factor analysis was employed to all scales, and factor loadings, eigenvalues, and variance explained are shown in Table 1.

Before the data collection, the questionnaire was pre-tested on 35 package tourists and reviewed by scholars specialized in experience to offer comments regarding item comprehensibility. The Cronbach's alpha values of package tour experience, overall package tour satisfaction, and behavioral intentions were well above 0.7, indicating an acceptable level of internal consistency (Cronbach, 1951).

Finally, the questionnaire was revised using an item analysis method and considered the comments of academic scholars, in which the research instrument had an acceptable level of content validity. The final revised questionnaire was applied to package tourists.

3.3 Sampling and Surveying

The first phase comprised a convenience sampling method which is a specific type of non-probability sampling technique to collect the field data. In the next phase, the authors obtained permission from the local authorities to collect data in the research area.

Two Ph.D. students studying in tourism management were hired and trained concerning research data collection techniques such as questionnaire administration and some procedures for inducing tourists to participate in the questionnaire. The questionnaire was administered at Istanbul destination and applied to package tourists.

The questionnaires used a direct face-to-face survey method by assistants owing to the higher response rates. The survey was conducted from November 2017 to January 2018. A total of 375 usable questionnaires were collected.

Table 1 shows the demographic characteristics of the respondents. The age of the respondents was equally distributed between 21-30 years; 55.9% were male; 51% were single; 82.9% had a university degree or higher; 63.3% were employed; income of the respondents distributed equally above 20.000; most of the respondents were from Asia and Europe.

Table 1. Participants' Sample Characteristics and Travel Behaviors.

Demographics		N	%	Travel Behaviors		N	%
Sex	Male	209	55,9	Mode of Travel	Alone	20	5,4
	Female	165	44,1		Family	226	60,9
Marital Status	Single	187	51		Friends	125	33,7
	Married	180	49	Number of times of participations in package tours	1-3	176	55,5
Age	21-30	182	51,9		4-7	113	35,6
	31-40	114	32,5		8+	28	8,8
	>40	55	15,7	Length of stay	1-3	44	12,2
Education Level	Primary	5	1,4		4-7	260	71,8
	High School	58	15,8		8+	58	16
	University	241	65,7	Number of participants	1-10	88	30,8
	Master and PhD	63	17,2		11-20	107	37,4
Nationality	Europe	106	29,4	21+	91	31,8	
	Asia	233	64,7	Number of times of visits	None	158	42,2
	Africa	3	0,8		1	110	29,4
	America	18	5		2-3	73	19,5
			4+		33	8,8	
Income (\$)	<20.000	34	10				
	20.000-35.000	108	31,8				
	35.001-50.000	122	35,9				
	>50.000	76	22,4				
Employment	Full time	229	63,3				
	Part time	61	16,9				
	Retired	17	4,7				
	Unemployed	55	15,2				

Source: own elaboration.

Table 1 also summarizes the respondents' travel behaviors. Over half (60,9%) of the sample participated in a package tour with family; 55.5% participated in between 1-3 people; 71.8 % of respondents stayed 4-7 days in the destination; 42.2% of respondents are first-time visitors and 58.8% are repeat tourists. Only one participant did not information about demographics and travel behaviors.

3.4 Data Analysis

The data were examined using SPSS 24.0 and SmartPLS 3 statistical software. SPSS was used to perform demographic profiles and travel behaviors of participants, exploratory factor analysis, and Cronbach's alpha (α) coefficient. Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) approach was applied to confirm and validate the structure of the constructs. Also, it was used due to its powerful, flexible, and sophisticated attributes in the model assessment to predict and test the theory compared to covariance-based SEM (Hair, Hollingsworth, Randolph, & Chong, 2017).

Furthermore, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) is tested with the best score in PLS-SEM (Afthanorhan, 2013), and it is assumed that data distributed with normality and thereby enable examination of the non-normal data by not considering small sample size (Chin & Newsted, 1999).

The outputs of the data can be tested with the Bootstrapping method (Hair, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2011). PLS-SEM has been widely used in hospitality and tourism research more recently (Hashemi, Marzuki, Mohammed, & Kiumarsi, 2020; Su, Johnson, & O'Mahony, 2020).

4 ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

An exploratory factor analysis was conducted (Table 2) using SPSS 24.0. A principal component analysis in exploratory factor analysis with Varimax rotation was conducted. The purpose of this process is to summarize items of all scales into a smaller set of dimensions (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013).

To increase the reliability of the package tour experience scale, inappropriate items such as "I felt a sense of harmony (e.g., arts, scenery, etc.) during the tour" and "It was fun to be on this tour" due to having a factor loading under 0.40. were removed from the factor of esthetic experience.

Also, the item "The tour was amazing" was removed from the factor of entertainment experience due to loading on two factors. Lastly, the item "I forgot about my daily routine during the tour." was removed from the factor of escapism experience due to having a factor loading under 0.40 (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013).

The elimination process of the package tour experience scale resulted in 14 items out of 18. On

the other hand, the satisfaction and behavioral intentions scales have been shown good results and were loaded on the same factor. The factor loadings of all items were greater than 0.5 (Hair, Anderson, Tatham, & Black, 1998).

Some procedures have been applied to present the quality of the research instrument. The Cronbach's alpha scores for the latent variables of, package tour experiences (educational, entertainment, escapism, and esthetic experience) were 0.934, 0.910, 0.861, and 0.798, respectively and overall package tour satisfaction was 0,930. Also, the coefficient α of behavioral intentions was 0.876.

All the scores exceeded the benchmark of the expected score (0.70) (Cronbach, 1951). Hence, these scores show that all of them had an acceptable level of internal consistency for items measuring the same construct. Also, composite reliability which is measured for internal consistency in constructs expects that all values should be higher than 0.70 (Bacon, Sauer, & Young, 1995), which values of composite reliability for each construct are higher than 0.70.

4.1 Measurement Model (outer model)

PLS-SEM generally follows a two-step process for the assessment of a model using including assessments of the measurement and the structural model (Hashemi et al., 2020). In the first phase, confirmatory factor analysis was conducted using SmartPLS (Table 2) to examine the relationships among constructs.

The main loadings of all items were above 0.70, which is recommended that it should be greater than the value of 0.5 (Hair et al., 2013). Then, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value of a factor is used to

investigate to evaluate the convergent validity of measures. For convergent validity, the scores of the average variance extracted (AVE) should be above 0.5.

Table 2 shows the data results and provide essential criteria (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Also, the model achieves a reasonable fit. According to model fit indices, the Normed-fit index (NFI) is 0.90, which the cut-off criteria should be $NFI \geq .95$ (Hu & Bentler, 1999) and Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) is 0.04 with a certain threshold ($SRMR < 0.08$). For the exact fit criteria, it is considered values of $d_ULS (.46)$ and $d_G (0.42)$, which shows the model well established (Henseler, Hubona, & Ray, 2016).

In this study, discriminant and convergent validity were used to evaluate construct validity. As stated above, convergent validity which measures the quantity of variance was evaluated through AVE and all scores of constructs were acceptable level.

Furthermore, it was also examined the discriminant validity. To evaluate discriminant validity, a comparison of cross-loadings and the square roots of the AVE was traditionally conducted. However, it was found out that "these techniques may not consistently detect the absence of discriminant validity, particularly in regular research conditions." (Hashemi et al., 2020, p. 9).

To overcome this issue, a new technique namely the Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio of correlation (HTMT) was recommended and proposed to evaluate discriminant validity.

Table 3 shows the discriminant validity evaluation of the measurement model HTMT values for each factor. HTMT values should be below 1 (Henseler et al., 2015) and all scores are below 1. Hence, it can be concluded that discriminant validity is well established for this measurement model.

Table 2. Internal consistency results of exploratory factor analysis (EFC). confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and reliability of factors

Factors	EFC		CFA					
	Factor loading	Eigenvalue	Variance explained(%)	Cronbach' s alpha	Outer loadings	CR	AVE	
The Package Tour Experience	Education		8.419	60.139	.934		0.93	0.78
	The package tour experience has made me more knowledgeable.	.723				0.92		
	I learned a lot during the tour.	.843				0.87		
	The package tour stimulated my curiosity to learn new things.	.852				0.87		
	The package tour experience was highly educational for me.	.818				0.87		
	Entertainment		1.298	9.274	.910		0.91	0.73
	The tour had surprising events	.678				0.78		
	The package tour was entertaining	.770				0.89		
	The tour was astonishing	.828				0.87		
	The tour was fascinating	.794				0.87		
Escapism		.898	6.412	.861		0.87	0.69	
The package tour transformed me in a good way	.754				0.88			

	The package tour made me forget my daily worries	.773					0.88	
	I felt a sense of freedom during the package tour	.777					0.72	
	Esthetic		.579	4.138	.798			0.80 0.57
	I really enjoyed seeing the environment during the tour.	.559					0.74	
	The tour was rich in beautiful scenery.	.647					0.74	
	Expression of local arts (e.g. Music handcrafts) was nice to see	.669					0.78	
	Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy: 0.938 Bartlett's Test of sphericity; 4371.349; p<0.000							
Overall Package Tour Satisfaction			3.325	83.118	.930			0.93 0.77
	This package tour met my expectations.	.933					0.91	
	Overall. I am satisfied with the package tour.	.912					0.85	
	I believe I received what was promised during the package tour.	.906					0.88	
	This package tour exceeded my expectations	.896					0.88	
	Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy: .856 Bartlett's Test of sphericity; 1241.370; p<0.000							
Behavioral Intentions			3.355	67.103	.876			0.88 0.59
	I would participate in this package tours in the future.	.84					0.83	
	I would buy a similar package tour again.	.80					0.75	
	I will share my experiences online with others when I return home.	.79					0.72	
	I will share my experiences with others when I return home.	.85					0.72	
	I would advise my friends to go on a guided tour.	.81						0.81
	Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy: 0.798 Bartlett's Test of sphericity; 1001.748; p<0.000							

Source: own elaboration.

Table 3. Discriminant validity of measurement model-Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

Construct	E	EN	ES	EST	S	BI
Education (E)						
Entertainment (EN)	0.70					
Escapism (ES)	0.74	0.74				
Esthetic (EST)	0.81	0.90	0.79			
Overall Package Tour Satisfaction (S)	0.66	0.70	0.68	0.82		
Behavioral Intention (BI)	0.63	0.65	0.63	0.76	0.89	

Source: own elaboration.

Table 4. Results on t-test between package tour experience, overall package tour satisfaction and behavioral intentions with first time and repeat tourists.

Variable	First Time Tourist		Repeat Tourist		Df	T	p	Result
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD				
Education	4.32	0.66	4.31	0.75	372	.158	.100	Not significant
Entertainment	4.09	0.71	4.01	0.74	372	.988	.807	Not significant
Escapism	4.13	0.70	4.05	0.83	372	.896	.170	Not significant
Esthetic	4.24	0.67	4.11	0.67	372	1.848	.957	Not significant
Satisfaction	4.07	0.72	3.94	0.73	372	1.613	.770	Not significant
Behavioral Intentions	4.16	0.66	4.07	0.73	372	1.189	.853	Not significant

Source: own elaboration.

4.2 The results of independent sample t-test

A t-test was used to examine the differences of

dimensions of package tour experience, overall package tour satisfaction, and behavioral intentions based on the first time and repeat tourists. Hence, there

was no significant difference between first time tourists' education experience ($M = 4.32, SD=0.66$), entertainment experience ($M = 4.09, SD=0.71$), escapism experience ($M = 4.13, SD=0.70$) and esthetic experience ($M = 4.24, SD=0.67$), and repeat tourists' education experience ($M = 4.31, SD=0.75$), entertainment experience ($M = 4.01, SD=0.74$), escapism experience ($M = 4.05, SD=0.83$) and esthetic experience ($M = 4.11, SD=0.67$).

So, the results suggest that the frequency of visits for the tourists had no impact on their overall package tour experience. Similarly, there were no significant differences between the first time ($M = 4.07, SD=0.72$) and repeaters ($M = 3.94, SD=0.73$) in terms of overall package tour satisfaction.

Furthermore, there were no significant differences between first time ($M = 4.16, SD=0.66$) and repeaters ($M = 3.4.07, SD=0.73$) in terms of behavioral intentions. Therefore, there was no relationship between all independent variables and visit frequency (first time and repeat tourists) as shown in Table 4.

4.3 Assessment of the structural model

PLS-SEM does not consider whether the data is distributed with normality or non-normal data with a small sample size (Chin & Newsted, 1999). Therefore, the outputs of the data are tested with the Bootstrapping method (Hair et al., 2011).

Indirect analyses were conducted to examine the mediating effects of overall package tour satisfaction on the relationship between the package tour experience and behavioral intentions (Iacobucci et al., 2007) with 5000 bootstrap samples and at the 95% confidence interval. In the structural models for first-timers ($N=158$) and repeaters ($N=216$), it was adopted this procedure. Table 6 shows the results of the structural models for first-time and repeat tourists.

According to results obtained from the structural models, the path coefficient of education experience on overall package tour satisfaction with the package tour was significant for first-time tourists ($\beta = .162, p=.044$) and was not significant for repeat tourists ($\beta = .109, p=.136$).

The first indirect effect, from education experience to behavioral intentions through overall package tour satisfaction, was significant and positive for first-timers ($\beta=.130, p=.043$); but it was insignificant for repeat tourists ($\beta=.133, p=.141$).

Tourists may want to be informed about the destination and its culture. The level of knowledge can determine overall tourist satisfaction (Song et al., 2015). Further to this, gaining more information during the trip, new skills, and new challenges from the trip can influence destination satisfaction (Gohary et al., 2020).

Based on the empirical findings of this study, it has been concluded that there is a difference between first-timers and repeaters in terms of the impact of education experience on overall package tour satisfaction.

While education experience from the package tour affects first-timers' overall package tour satisfaction, education experience from the package tour does not affect repeaters' overall package tour satisfaction.

We can explain it as the satisfaction level of repeaters is consolidated and their interest may have changed for another experience (Shavanddasht & Allan, 2018). This finding for first-timers is in line with past studies and a plethora of studies have revealed that the education experience has a direct impact on overall package tour satisfaction (Oh, Fiore, & Jeoung, 2007; Hosany & Witham, 2009; Ho & Tsai, 2011; Quadri-Felitti & Fiore, 2013; Song et al., 2015; Mahdzar et al., 2017; Gohary et al., 2020).

According to Gohary et al. (2020), destination satisfaction mediates on the relationship between knowledge experience and behavioral intentions. Similarly, overall package tour satisfaction only was mediated between education experience and behavioral intentions for first-timers.

As stated above, many destinations apply different marketing strategies to attract more potential visitors (Lin & Morais, 2010). This finding could be extremely useful for attracting first-timers or potential visitors (Gohary et al., 2020).

Entertainment experience on overall package tour satisfaction with the package tour was not significant for first-time tourists ($\beta = .142, p=.093$) and repeat tourists ($\beta = .159, p=.062$). Further, from entertainment experience to behavioral intentions through overall package tour satisfaction, was insignificant (first-timers: $\beta = .114, p=.096$; repeat tourists: $\beta = .133, p=.064$).

Entertainment experience is regarded as tourist's passive observes towards activities and performances of others such as listening to music from buskers or participating in a local music festival during their trip (Pine & Gilmore, 1999; Oh et al., 2007).

Cultural and heritage attractions push tourists to visit the destination and these may help to increase tourists' entertainment experience (Quadri-Felitti & Fiore, 2013). When considered that Istanbul offers a wide range of tourist attractions (natural and cultural) for both package and individual tourists, these can be led to create considerable performances and activities in the destination.

Moreover, tourist loyalty depends on activities and performances staged at the destination (Chi & Qu, 2008). According to findings, this research concluded that entertainment does not influence overall package

tour satisfaction (Oh et al., 2007; Mahdzar et al., 2017) and mediate between entertainment experience and behavioral intentions for both groups.

This can be due to the lack of variety of activities and performances provided at the destination for package tourists or limited time offered for the package tours as the tour programs are full of historical places and museums to be visited so that visitors may not have enough time for entertainment.

Escapism experience on overall package tour satisfaction with the package tour was not significant for first-time tourists ($\beta=.143$, $p=.128$) and was significant for repeat tourists ($\beta=.204$, $p=.046$).

Moreover, from escapism experience to behavioral intentions through overall package tour satisfaction, was insignificant for first-timers ($\beta=.115$, $p=.128$); but it was significant and positive for repeat tourists ($\beta=.169$, $p=.046$).

Tourists generally demand to escape from their daily routine to learn something new from the destination that they visit. This questing provides tourists to have a memorable tourist experience (Kim et al., 2012). The dimension of escapist requires greater immersion and participation than other realms of the tourism experience. It is a real connection with the destination environment (Oh et al., 2007). This dimension is also one of the most used motivational factors in the tourism and recreation fields (Andreu et al., 2006).

According to this study, it was found out that escapism experience only impacts the overall package tour satisfaction of repeaters. Moreover, it mediates between escapism experience and behavioral intentions of repeaters. First-timers gives no importance to the escapism experience during the package tour.

These findings for repeaters is consistent with previous studies (Xu & Chan, 2010; Park, Oh, & Park, 2010; Mahdzar et al., 2017). It can also be said that escapism experience is the most important dimension for repeaters and for destination managers as tourist memorable experience is an important motivator of their repeat visit.

Esthetic experience on overall package tour satisfaction with the package tour was for first-time tourists ($\beta=.379$, $p=.000$) and repeat tourists ($\beta=.380$,

$p=.000$). Furthermore, from esthetic experience to behavioral intentions through overall package tour satisfaction, was significant and positive (first-timers: $\beta=.305$, $p=.001$; repeat tourists: $\beta=.316$, $p=.000$). Among the dimensions of package tourism experience, the esthetic experience is regarded as the most influential dimension on overall package tour satisfaction for first-timers and repeaters.

According to this result, tourists are passive in esthetic experiences but immersed in the package experience. Esthetic experience is considered an important component of destination evaluations and the overall experience (Oh et al., 2007). Bonn et al. (2007) noted that the physical environment of heritage attractions plays a significant role in tourists' behaviors and behavioral intentions. Hosany and Witham (2009) concluded in their study esthetics was the major determinant of tourism experience outcomes.

Furthermore, Istanbul was registered on the World Heritage Sites List by UNESCO since 1985 and has great potential in terms of heritage attractions. In particular, Istanbul has a historical and cultural background from the ottoman and the byzantine period.

There are many buildings, monuments, fountains, landmarks, mosques, churches and synagogues, towers, bathhouses, parks and gardens, and historical shopping places dating back to Ottoman and the Byzantine period and these different aesthetic elements may affect tourist's aesthetic experience (Gezici & Kerimoglu, 2010).

Therefore, this finding seems to be consistent with another research (Oh et al., 2007; Ho & Tsai, 2011; Quadri-Felitti & Fiore, 2013; Mehmetoglu & Engen, 2011; Mahdzar et al., 2017).

Collectively, the results for dimensions of package tour experience provide evidence confirming that education and esthetic experience affects overall package tour satisfaction for first-time tourists whereas entertainment and esthetic experience affects overall package tour satisfaction for repeat tourists.

These significant results are positively related to overall package tour satisfaction. Furthermore, overall package tour satisfaction affects and positively related to the behavioral intentions of package tourists ($\beta=.804$, $p=.000$).

Table 5. Group differences (first-time vs. repeat package tourists).

Independent to dependent	First Time Tourist		Repeat Tourist	
	β	P	β	P
Education > Overall Package Tour Satisfaction	.162	.044	.109	.136
Entertainment > Overall Package Tour Satisfaction	.142	.093	.159	.062
Escapism > Overall Package Tour Satisfaction	.143	.128	.204	.046
Esthetic-> Overall Package Tour Satisfaction	.379	.000	.380	.000
Overall Package Tour Satisfaction > Behavioral Intention	.804	.000	.832	.000

Education > Overall Package Tour Satisfaction > Behavioral Intention	.130	.043	.091	.141
Entertainment > Overall Package Tour Satisfaction > Behavioral Intention	.114	.096	.133	.064
Escapism > Overall Package Tour Satisfaction > Behavioral Intention	.115	.128	.169	.046
Esthetic > Overall Package Tour Satisfaction > Behavioral Intention	.305	.001	.316	.000

R2 (Overall Package Tour Satisfaction) = .597 (first timers); .594 (repeaters).

R2 (Behavioral Intention) = .807 (first timers); .692 (repeaters).

Source: own elaboration.

All significant indirect effects of results are a complete mediation or full mediation (Hayes, 2009). Hypotheses results for both groups are seen in Table

6. Furthermore, structural models for first-timers and repeaters are presented in Figure 1 and Figure 2, respectively.

Fig. 1. Structural model for first time tourists

Source: own elaboration.

Fig. 2. Structural model for repeat tourists

Source: own elaboration.

Tourists participating in package tours expect to experience positive emotions. Tourists satisfied by their tour experience will be happy with the package tour and destination. So, their intention to repurchase the package tour and recommend the destination to others will be improved and the destination will be promoted widely by tourist word-of-mouth recommendations.

In this study, it was also concluded that satisfaction with package tour experience positively affects the behavioral intentions of participants. There are many studies conducted on the relationship between satisfaction and loyalty behaviors and previous research has established that satisfaction is an important determinant of behavioral intentions (Baker & Crompton, 2000; Kozak & Rimmington, 2000; Bigne et al., 2001; Duman & Mattila, 2005; Yoon & Uysal, 2005; Chen & Tsai, 2007; Chi & Qu, 2008; Chen & Chen, 2010; Xu & Chan, 2010; Sun et al., 2013; Prayag et al., 2013; Lin & Kuo, 2016; Ghorbanzade et al., 2019; Gohary et al., 2020).

5 FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The fundamental purpose of this study is to reveal the effect of package tour experience on overall package tour satisfaction and to explore the mediating effects of overall package tour satisfaction on the relationship between package tour experiences and behavioral intentions for first-timers and repeaters to Istanbul.

Another key aim of this article is to examine the differences and similarities between first-timers and repeaters. Despite the importance of package tours for destinations and travel companies in terms of effective marketing strategies, there have been no studies in the existing literature about investigating first-timers and repeaters' package tour experience within the framework of the experience economy model of Pine and Gilmore (1999).

Thus, it can be said that the findings emerged are original for the current literature. This study has therefore several meaningful implications for tourism research literature. The results here show that the different dimensions of package tour experience affect the tourists' level of satisfaction and behavioral intentions

Several studies so far have investigated the differences between first-time and repeat tourists, but no studies have examined package tourists experience, overall package tour satisfaction, and behavioral intentions the differences, similarities, and mediating effects of overall package tour satisfaction on the relationship between package tour experiences and behavioral intentions for the first time and repeat package tourists.

The findings of this study showed that there were no significant differences between first-time and repeat package tourists in their package tourists' experience, overall package tour satisfaction, and behavioral intentions.

Although there have been many studies examining package tour in the tourism literature (Geva & Goldman, 1991; Ross & Iso-Ahola, 1991; Bowie & Chang, 2005; Chang, 2006; Fomiatti, 2008; Chang, 2009; Huang, Hsu & Chan, 2010; Xu & Chan, 2010; Lee et al., 2011; Caber & Albayrak, 2018), no studies related to examining the dimensions of the tourist experience in terms of the package tour.

This study is the first study to investigate in detail package tourists' experience and to explore the relationship between overall package satisfaction and behavioral intentions for first time and repeat package tourists as well as differences between these groups. Therefore, this study seeks to obtain data that will help to fill this research gap.

The findings of this study present managerial insights for tour companies and destination planners. Based on the findings, tour operators which manage the tour performance should give importance to enhance the educational experience in the tours for tourists who visit the destination for the first time.

They can add some activities based on learning for making tourists more knowledgeable and stimulate tourists to get new insight into the local culture of the destination. This aspect of the tour experience makes tourists more satisfied with the tours and destination. Also, satisfied tourists could prefer the same package tour and destination in the next time.

Thus, we can say that enhancing educational experience should be a major goal for destination managers and tour operators. On the other hand, repeat tourists escape from the daily routine to visit the same destination with the same package tour. as the findings of this study did not find any relation with repeat visitors.

We can still say that to build a strong relationship between destination, package tour, and repeat tourists, package tours should be redesigned to include innovative or creative experience so that repeat tourists' education experience could be enhanced. Also, tour operators can generate managerial strategies and operate package tour processes by including new educational experiences for repeaters and they can also separate the package tours according to tourists' frequency of visit.

Esthetic experience is of great importance for both repeat and first-time package tourists. Since we describe the esthetic experience as situations and objects of esthetic interest are specified as fundamentally different from everyday situations and

objects of everyday use (Marković, 2012), we should design the destination and package tours as a component of the unique experience that the destination can offer for their visitor as they can experience something new and fundamentally different from everyday situations and objects of everyday use.

5.1 Limitations and Future Research

The current study suggests implications for future research. First, this study examined the effects of the package tour experience on package tour satisfaction and behavioral intentions in a specific location of Istanbul, Turkey. The findings of these package tour experiences are destination-specific and cannot be generalized for all destinations.

Future research may be conducted in other destinations to strengthen the relationship between these constructs for enhancing the generalizability of findings.

Secondly, this study examined only the package tour experience construct (independent variable) affecting package tour satisfaction and behavioral intentions. It may not provide a comprehensive understanding of the determinants of behavioral intentions.

Further research should be undertaken to investigate important variables for the destination such as the package tour quality and perceived tour value.

Furthermore, it was stated that the package tour is influenced by previous experiences, expectations, and unpredictable events. In future investigations, it might be possible to use these constructs to measure the package tour satisfaction.

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